

TRANSFORMING OPEN RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION THROUGH CHARM TORCH

DELIVERABLE D10.1 – TORCH: WEBSITE

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22-03-2021	V1	Prof. Gemma Marfany (UB), Prof. Raul Ramos, Nicole Font (UB), Jaime Llorca (UB)	Web structure and first version of the content.
25-03-2021	V2	WP members (Project Management Team)	Discussion and review comments. PMT approval.
26-03-2021	V3	Vice Rectors Committee.	Discussion and review comments. VRs approval.
29-03-2021	V4	Prof. Gemma Marfany (UB), Nicole Font (UB), Jaime Llorca (UB)	Final version.

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1. WEBSITE ADDRESS

The TORCH website can be found at: <https://www.charm-eu.eu/torch>. Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the website's home.

Figure 1. TORCH website (screenshot).

2. WEBSITE STRUCTURE & CONTENT

The following section shows TORCH's website structure (Table 1), as well as a brief description of its content.

Table 1. TORCH website structure and main content.

Web Menu	Content Description
0 Home	Project presentation, shortcuts to relevant information, latest news.
1 About Us	Information about the project organization and structure.
1.1 Who We Are	TORCH and CHARM-Eu members.
1.2 What We Do	TORCH as the R&I dimension of CHARM-EU. Cross Cutting Principles and Transformational Modules.
1.3 The CHARM-EU Alliance	Background about CHARM-EU.
1.4 Organizational Structure	Governance and management (Rectors Assembly, Vice Rectors Committee, Project Management Team, Quality Committee).
1.5 Associate Partners	List of Associate Partners.
2 Objectives & Main Results	Description of project aims. Detailed description of Work Packages and deliverables.
2.1 Aim of the project	TORCH general goals and specific objectives.
2.2 Work Packages Description and Deliverables	Detailed description of each WP. Deliverables description (available for download).
3 News & Events	News related to TORCH, dissemination output, events.
4 Press room	Newsletter, press releases, communication kit, social media.
5 Related Projects	European Universities Initiative, List of European Universities, links to other similar and related projects.
6 Contact	Contact form, email address.